

STUDY ON THE MORPHOLOGY OF THE POLYURETHANE SYNTHESIZED FROM 4,4' – DIPHENYLMETHANE DIISOCYANATE AND POLY(TETRAMETHYLENE GLYCOL)

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1 Introduction

Polyurethanes are a broad class of materials utilized in a wide variety of applications. One major application of polyurethanes is in the area of flexible foams. Through controlling the morphology, manufacturers currently produce some low-density foams that feel as soft as down and other “foams” that are essentially high-strength, bubble-free elastomeric castings. This range of properties has allowed flexible polyurethane foams to attain the sixth position in sales volume relative to all major plastics. As widely utilized as flexible polyurethane foams have become, clear scientific understanding of how changes in formulation ultimately lead to properties is still far from complete. This is partly due to the “technological” approach taken in the past in developing processing techniques, but it is also largely due to the complex nature of these materials.[1] Many advances have occurred in the collective knowledge of how morphology develops based on formulation, and this has led to a better understanding of how those various structures lead to properties. Polyurethane synthesized from diisocyanate, polyol and diol or diamine as the chain extender. The most commonly used polyols are polyethers, polyester polyols. On the other hand, methylene diphenyl diisocyanate (MDI), hydrogenated MDI (H12MDI), toluene diisocyanate (TDI), isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI), xylene diisocyanate (XDI), and 1,5-naphthalene diisocyanate (NDI) are widely used diisocyanates in polyurethane formulations. By controlling the composition of each component, two solid state phases frequently result. This two phase morphology provides the key to controlling performance of the final product and gives the manufacturer versatility in tuning properties as desired by varying the composition or content of one or other phases. One of the phases is

soft segments. This phase consisted of polyol. Another of the phases is hard segments. This phase consisted of diisocyanate and chain extender. Depending on the thermal properties of these segments, the hard segment and soft segment mixing or separation occurs. So the change of segmented structure has been reported [2]. Vilensky and Lipatov [3] was a review of polymer - polymer interaction parameter and degree of correlation between the phase separation. A number of studies have dealt with the physical cross-linking caused by chemical cross-linking and the hydrogen bonding of chemical bond between the segment according to the molecular structure and functional groups of diisocyanate and polyol because physical cross-linking heavily influences properties of polyurethane. Kontou [4] conducted a study on the change of chemical bonding and the hydrogen bonding caused by the ratio of diisocyanate and polyol using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR).

In the study, polyurethane synthesized from 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI), poly(tetramethylene glycol), and 1,4-butane diol (BD), dibutyltin dilaurate (DBTL) as the catalyst are investigated using FT-IR.

All reactions were carried out in 4-neck round bottomed flask fitted with dropping funnel, condenser, gas inlet and thermometer.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

MDI (4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate) were purchased from German BASF Company. Polyether polyols (PTMG) (Mw 2000) were purchased from Aldrich. PTMG was treated with vacuum

dehydration at 60°C for 12 hours. 1,4-butanediol were purchased from Aldrich.

2.2 Preparation of sample and characterization

MDI monomer added into flasks. The temperature was increased up to melt MDI stirring under N₂ atmosphere. Then the polyether polyol (PTMG) was added into MDI flask. After 2 hours reaction, the MDI-based pre-polymer were prepared. The MDI-based pre-polymer was sealed under 90°C. Measured MDI pre-polymer, chain extender, 1,4-butanediol and other additives were polyethylene-based plastic cup and then stirred strongly with a rate of 2500rpm. Mixing time was 1 minute 30 seconds. And the catalyst is added after stirring 1 minute. The mole ratios between polyol, diisocyanate and chain extender diol were varied from 1:2:1 to 1:23:22 as Table 1. A polymer made from 1 mol of PTMG, 2 mol of MDI, and 1 mol of BD is designated as PU-2. IR spectroscopy (Perkin Elmer - spectrum 100) was used to determine the change of hydrogen bonding in polyurethane.

3 Result and discussion

One of the important factors of the change of the properties of the polyurethane is cross-linking. There are two types of cross-linking that physical cross-linking by hydrogen bonds and chemical cross-linking by chemical bonds. The hydrogen bonding takes place between C=O stretching band and N-H stretching band. The case of polyether polyol or polyester polyol exists hydrogen bonding between the hard segment and soft segment. FT-IR is a powerful tool for study of hydrogen bonding. The peak of C=O stretching band and N-H stretching band is separated with hydrogen bonded peak and non-hydrogen bonded peak. Therefore, the degree of hydrogen bonding can be observed [3-5]. Table 2 shows data from reference of the peak of C=O stretching band and N-H stretching band. In general, FT-IR peaks are known that shift from high frequency to low frequency when hydrogen bonding occurs or increase of degree of hydrogen bond.

Figure 1 shows the peak of N-H stretching band. The peak of N-H stretching band shift from 3328 cm⁻¹ to 3324 cm⁻¹ with increasing hard segment content. The shift of the stretching peaks of N-H indicates that the degree of hydrogen bonding is increased by increasing N-H group and C=O group. Figure 2 shows the peak of C=O stretching band

shift from 1728 cm⁻¹ to 1721 cm⁻¹ for the same reason.

Thermal analysis was carried out on a Perkin Elmer DSC-4000. DSC scans were started at -80°C.

In this study the glass transition temperature of polyether polyol was determined at -47.5°C. And Tg of consisting of MDI and BD polyurethane was determined at 145.2°C. The Tg of the polyurethane synthesized from Polyether polyol, MDI, and BD was determined at 78.7 °C ~ 120.2 °C. The glass transition temperature tend to increasing by increasing of hard segment content. Figure 3 shows the Tg calculated from Fox equation of polyurethane. Fox equation is generally used to predict the Tg of the block copolymer and miscible polymer blend.

$$\frac{1}{T_g} = \frac{w_1}{T_{g1}} + \frac{w_2}{T_{g2}} \quad (1)$$

Where Tg = The glass transition temperature of polyurethane

Tg1 = Tg of polyether polyol

Tg2 = Tg of consisting of MDI and BD polyurethane

W1 = Tg of soft segment

W2 = Tg of hard segment

Figure 3 shows significant differences between the dotted line of fox equation and the Tg observed by DSC.

4 Conclusions

Morphology and thermal properties of polyurethane synthesized from 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI), poly(tetramethylene glycol), and 1,4-butane diol (BD) are investigated using fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), differential scanning calorimeter (DSC). From the FT-IR study, it is found that the stretching peaks of hydrogen bonded N-H and C=O are shifted to the low frequencies with the increase of hard segment content of the polyurethane. The shift of the stretching peaks of hydrogen bonding is increased. From the DSC study, it appears that the glass transition temperature (Tg)

of the polyurethane is increased with the increase of the hard segment content.

Table 1. Chemical composition and hard segment content for the polyurethanes

Sample code	Molar Ratio			Hard segment Weight percent ^a (%)
	Polyol	MDI	BD	
PU-2	1	2	1	22.8
PU-3	1	3	2	31.7
PU-5	1	5	4	44.6
PU-6	1	6	5	49.4
PU-10	1	10	9	62.3
PU-16	1	16	15	72.8
PU-23	1	23	22	79.4

a) calculated as weight percentage of MDI and BD per total polymer weight.

Table 2. Frequency of the N – H stretching and C=O stretching mode

Group	Wave number (Cm ⁻¹)	
	Non-hydrogen bonded	hydrogen bonded
N – H	3448 ~ 3440 ^a	3347 ~ 3300 ^a
C = O	1734 ~ 1731 ^b	1725 ~ 1715 ^b

a) data from reference [4]

b) data from reference [5]

Fig 1. FT-IR spectra of the N-H stretching region of the polyurethanes synthesized from PTMG, BD and MDI.

Fig 2. FT-IR spectra of the C=O stretching region of the polyurethanes synthesized from PTMG, BD and MDI.

Fig 3. Tg of the polyurethane synthesized from from PTMG, BD and MDI : (·) observed by DSC; (---) calculated by using equation (1).

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